

FOREST4EU partner: StMELF-LWF

OG: Agroforst in Österreich (Agroforestry in Austria)

OG's country: Austria

Type of Innovation: Organisational innovation

“Agroforestry in Austria” Network

Introduction

The progressing climatic change in the regions dominated by arable farming in East Austria cause agricultural holdings to test new growing methods, among them also agroforestry systems. In Austria there are, only few examples of implementation. There was no contact point for interested agricultural holdings, nor a network for the exchange of information and experience between practice and science. The OG has therefore created the practice-based “Agroforestry in Austria” network. It includes six arable farms with an interest in implementing farm-adapted agroforestry systems. The network makes insights from this pioneer work to other farms and multipliers available.

The network

The OG created the multi-actor "Agroforestry in Austria" network, consisting of the 6 participating farms with an interest in developing agroforestry systems on their land. Moreover, farms with established agroforestry systems, the strategic partners of the OG (see above), and other interested groups were also involved. The network brings different types of knowledge together, incl. farming practice, scientific and advisory expertise on agroforestry systems, administrative and RDP-related knowledge, and knowledge transfer know how. It organizes field trips and learning from good practice examples (e.g. in Switzerland, supported by OG partner), provides knowledge and information on agroforestry systems, facilitates interaction and collaboration, and creates visibility for the topic in Austria. The network activities are mainly project-financed, thus lacking a solid basis.

Communication activities are key to the network. The OG coordinator FiBL Austria (Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) sustains the "Agroforestry in Austria" network through its website <https://agroforst-oesterreich.at/> and follow-up projects. More information is available on YouTube and in published articles.

Lessons learned

Establishing the agroforestry network in Austria created multiple benefits: a contact point for questions and issues related to agroforestry, stronger interest and demand from practitioners, awareness among decisionmakers for agroforestry as a means for land management with climate and nature and pulling relevant

agroforestry knowledge for Austria together. The networking and opportunities to meet like-minded people reduce initial barriers, making it easier for practitioners to implement agroforestry systems. Foreign know-how is channeled to Austria and made available.

What went well? Cooperation in the network, openness of involved parties, and exchange of knowledge and experience with practitioners from Austria and other countries.

What should be improved? Pay more attention to farming seasons when planning for meetings and workshops (to enhance opportunities for participation of all stakeholders), increase resources for networking, and involve decision makers earlier.

Figure 1: Field excursion of agroforestry network in Austria (@ Markut Theresia/FIBL)

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://agroforst-oesterreich.at/projekte/>

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